

Larval nutritional-stress and tolerance to extreme temperatures in the peach fruit fly,
Bactrocera zonata (Diptera: Tephritidae)

Ben-Yosef, M.¹, Altman, Y.¹, Nemni-Lavi, E.¹, Papadopoulos, N.² and Nestel, D^{1*}

¹Department of Entomology, Institute of Plant Protection, Agricultural Research
Organization, Israel.

² Laboratory of Entomology and Agricultural Zoology, Department of Agriculture
Crop Production and Rural Environment, University of Thessaly, Volos, Greece

* Corresponding author: Dept. of Entomology, Institute of Plant Protection, ARO,
The Volcani Center, Rishon Letzion, Israel. nestel@agri.gov.il